

Synthesis of magnetic nanoparticles and their effect on growth of carbon nanotubes

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Abstract : A series of spinel ferrite nanoparticles viz. manganese ferrite (MnFe_2O_4), zinc ferrite (ZnFe_2O_4), cobalt ferrite (CoFe_2O_4) and nickel ferrite (NiFe_2O_4) were prepared by solvothermal process. X-Ray diffraction patterns show that the synthesized ferrite samples are pure without any impurities. The as-prepared ferrites were further used as a precursor catalyst for the growth of CNTs using thermal chemical vapor deposition (CVD) technique. Results show that these ferrites acted as effective catalysts for the growth of carbon nanotubes. The as-grown nanotubes were studied by electron microscope (FE-SEM). Further studies like Raman spectroscopy and VSM analysis were also done to evaluate the properties of the as-prepared catalyst and the as-grown carbon nanotubes.

Keywords : Magnetic nanoparticles, carbon nanotubes, spinel ferrites, thermal chemical vapor deposition.

Introduction

Carbon nanotubes are 1D in nature having a great impact towards research community. The surface, electronic, chemical, physical and mechanical properties of this material owes to many applications. Thermal chemical vapor deposition is one of the most popular techniques for the growth of CNTs with the catalyst and the precursor gas as source materials¹. Traditional catalysts used for the growth of CNTs are transition metal ions (Fe, Co, Ni) and their alloys. There are many reports based on these metals and supporting materials which include materials such as molybdenum and tungsten for increasing the yield of CNTs² with only a few papers on ferrite based CNTs. Spinel ferrites are one of the fascinating materials for the growth of carbon nanotubes. Basically these are of AFe_2O_4 ferrites (where A = Mn, Zn, Co, Ni), the metallic cations A^{2+} and Fe^{3+} occupy octahedral and tetrahedral sites. Depending upon the occupying sites the spinel nature will have an effect on their properties, such as catalytic activity, magnetic property and conductivity³⁻⁶. The catalytic activity of the spinel

ferrites was tested for some reactions such as oxidation of carbon monoxide, chemical compositions, crystal structure, electrochemical, electronic, decomposition of hydrogen peroxide and micro structural factors that have been found. The spinel ferrites are basically nano-sized particles and hence these can be widely used for growth of CNTs.

Present work is focused on the study of catalytic effect on the growth of CNTs using a series of different spinel ferrites by thermal chemical vapor deposition technique. A series of spinel ferrite nanoparticles viz. manganese ferrite (MnFe_2O_4), zinc ferrite (ZnFe_2O_4), cobalt ferrite (CoFe_2O_4) and nickel ferrite (NiFe_2O_4) were prepared by solvothermal process. Further the structure and morphological studies of catalyst and the as-prepared carbon nanotubes have been investigated by XRD, FE-SEM and Raman analysis.

Results and discussion

XRD analysis :

XRD patterns of the as-synthesized ferrites are shown

in Fig. 1A. The major XRD diffraction peaks for MnFe_2O_4 were observed at $2\theta = 30.18^\circ, 35.46^\circ, 43.02^\circ, 53.81^\circ, 56.81^\circ$ and 63.25° with the planes of (220), (311), (400), (422), (333) and (440) matching with the JCPDS Card No. 74-2403. The major XRD peaks for ZnFe_2O_4 , CoFe_2O_4 and NiFe_2O_4 were observed at $2\theta = 30.20^\circ, 35.46^\circ, 43.02^\circ, 53.81^\circ, 56.80^\circ$ and 63.25° with the corresponding lattice planes of (220), (311), (400), (422), (511) and (440) which are matching with the JCPDS Card No. 22-1012, 22-1086 and 86-2267 respectively. Fig. 1B shows the XRD of the purified carbon nanotubes prepared from the four ferrites as catalysts. The major peaks are observed at 26.05° and 43.7° corresponding to the hexagonal graphitic structures (002) and (101). Also could be seen is that there are no other peaks corresponding to any impurities.

Fig. 1. (A) XRD of four different catalysts and (B) carbon nanotubes after purification.

VSM and Raman analysis :

Fig. 2 shows the magnetic property of the as-synthesized ferrites (Fig. 2A). The magnetic properties of the as-prepared ferrites were characterized by VSM analysis at room temperature. The saturation magnetization (M_s) of MnFe_2O_4 , ZnFe_2O_4 , CoFe_2O_4 and NiFe_2O_4 was calculated to be 57.56, 7.14, 49.55 and 36.10 emu/g. As compared to all the four ferrites, ZnFe_2O_4 magnetic nanoparticles is having very less magnetic saturation due to the zero magnetic moment of the Zn^{2+} cations, and anti-ferromagnetic interactions between the Fe^{3+} cations in the octahedral sites causes the magnetic moment for ZnFe_2O_4 formula to vanish. The low magnetic nature is because of the small size of the nanoparticles and the presence of ions on the surface. Neel's magnetism theory explains this nature⁷.

Raman spectroscopy has proved to be a popular non-

destructive technique which was successfully used for the characterization of carbon based materials. The quality of the as-grown CNTs from four different ferrites was analyzed by Raman spectroscopy (Fig. 2B). In the case of CNTs, two narrow bands exist. Two main peaks D-band and G-band were generally used to characterize the CNT structures. The G-band varies in between $1580\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (which is ascribed to E_{2g} mode) and a second D-band at 1350 cm^{-1} (which is ascribed to A_{1g} mode) which only becomes active in the presence of disorder. For all the four ferrites, D-band and G-band appeared at 1347 and 1582 cm^{-1} with a little variation. The ratio of the intensity of D-band (I_D) to the intensity of G-band (I_G) is to measure the defects present in the as-prepared CNTs. The calculated ratios of the as-prepared CNTs in this experiment are showing less than 1, which indicates less amount of defects present in the as-prepared CNTs. The corresponding ratios as calculated for CNTs prepared from MnFe_2O_4 , ZnFe_2O_4 , CoFe_2O_4 and NiFe_2O_4 calculated to be 0.26, 0.35, 0.25 and 0.5 respectively. As compared with all four, CoFe_2O_4 ferrite shows the better quality of CNTs (less I_D/I_G ratio), which was further confirmed by FE-SEM and XRD analysis.

Fig. 2. (A) VSM analysis of four different catalysts and (B) Raman spectra of carbon nanotubes prepared from (a) MnFe_2O_4 (b) ZnFe_2O_4 , (c) CoFe_2O_4 and (d) NiFe_2O_4 catalysts after purification.

FE-SEM images of catalyst and CNTs :

Fig. 3 shows the FE-SEM images of the as-prepared catalyst and the as-grown carbon nanotubes by thermal chemical vapor deposition techniques. Fig. 3a₁ shows the MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles with the size of $\sim 100\text{--}200\text{ nm}$ and Fig. 3(a₂, a₃, a₄) shows the corresponding CNT growth of MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles. Similarly Fig. 3(b₁, c₁, d₁) shows the ZnFe_2O_4 , CoFe_2O_4 and NiFe_2O_4 nanoparticles with the size of $\sim 100\text{--}200\text{ nm}$ and the similar CNT growth

Fig. 3. FE-SEM images of as-prepared catalyst (a_1 , b_1 , c_1 , d_1) and CNTs after purification (a_2 , a_3 , a_4) $MnFe_2O_4$, (b_2 , b_3 , b_4) $ZnFe_2O_4$, (c_2 , c_3 , c_4) $CoFe_2O_4$ and (d_2 , d_3 , d_4) $NiFe_2O_4$.

of these particles are shown in Fig. 3(b_2 , b_3 , b_4), Fig. 3(c_2 , c_3 , c_4) and Fig. 3(d_2 , d_3 , d_4) respectively. The as-grown carbon nanotubes are uniform with an average diameter of 50–80 nm. The as-grown CNTs were predicted as multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) though HRTEM need to be done to confirm it further. Among all the four ferrites, $CoFe_2O_4$ gave a high yield of carbon nanotubes with less amorphous carbon as observed by FE-SEM images and Raman spectra.

Experimental

The typical procedure for preparing ferrite nanoparticles: $MnFe_2O_4$ was synthesized from $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $MnCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ as a starting material and for other ferrites instead of manganese chloride we varied $ZnCl_2$, $CoCl_2$ and $NiCl_2$ from our previous work⁸. The growth of nanotubes was carried out using thermal CVD technique. Acetylene gas was used as a carbon precursor. Detailed procedure is given in our previous reports².

The morphology of the CNTs were characterized by FE-SEM (JEOL, JSM-5610, 10 kV), and Raman spectroscopy (BRUKER RFS 27 : Stand alone FT-Raman

Spectrometer, Nd : YAG excited at 1064 nm). XRD was used to find the crystalline structure of catalysts as well as CNTs ($CuK\alpha_1$, $\lambda = 1.5604 \text{ \AA}$, Bruker, D8).

Conclusion

A series of spinel ferrite nanoparticles viz. manganese ferrite ($MnFe_2O_4$), zinc ferrite ($ZnFe_2O_4$), cobalt ferrite ($CoFe_2O_4$) and nickel ferrite ($NiFe_2O_4$) were prepared through solvothermal process. All the four ferrite catalysts were studied under XRD, VSM and FE-SEM analysis. Further, with the afore-prepared ferrites, CNTs were grown using thermal CVD technique. For the source of carbon, we used acetylene gas along with the nitrogen gas carrier. Among all the ferrites $CoFe_2O_4$ ferrite shows the good catalytic activity towards the growth of carbon nanotubes. The morphology of CNTs was characterized using FE-SEM, XRD and Raman analysis.

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References

1. W. Q. Deng, X. Xu and W. A. Goddard, *Nano Letters*, 2004, **4**, 2331.
2. C. Santhosh, M. Saranya, S. Felix, R. Ramachandran, N. Pradeep, V. Uma and A. Nirmala Grace, *J. Nano. Res.*, 2013, **24**, 46.
3. T. A. S. Ferreira, J. C. Waerenborgh, M. H. R. M. Mendonca, M. R. Nunes and F. M. Costa, *Sol. State Sci.*, 2003, **5**, 383.
4. F. S. Xu, X. F. Liu and S. D. Tse, *Carbon*, 2006, **44**, 570.
5. T. W. Tombler, C. Zhou, L. Alexseyev, J. Kong, H. Dai, L. Liu, C. S. Jayanthi, M. Tang and S. Y. Wu, *Nature*, 2000, **405**, 769.
6. P. M. Parthangal, R. E. Cavicchi and M. R. Zachariah, *Nanotechnology*, 2007, **18**, 185605.
7. L. Néel, *Ann. Phys. Paris*, 1948, **3**, 137.
8. C. Santhosh, J. Ann Miriam, T. Malathy, M. Saranya, R. Ramachandran, S. Felix, T. Mudaliar Vanchinathan, V. Velmurugan and A. Nirmala Grace, *Nanosci. Nanotech.-Asia*, 2013, **3**, 120.